

Research Article

Risk assessment of landslides: Low probability scenario for the town of Kavarna, northern Black Sea coast of Bulgaria

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Abstract

As part of the Reimbursable Advisory Services on Accelerating Resilience to Disaster Risks, the World Bank worked with the Interior Ministry of Bulgaria to develop a proposal for the National Disaster Risk Profile of Bulgaria. The purpose of this document, which is the fourth technical annex to the proposal for the National Disaster Risk Profile, is to provide particular conclusions, information, and techniques that were utilised to evaluate the risk of landslides in Bulgaria. For the first time at the national level, landslide risk assessment procedures based on ISO/IEC 31010:2019 Risk assessment techniques are being developed and applied in Bulgaria. The five primary categories in which the results are presented are physical safety, economic security, social well-being, environmental security, and security of tangible assets and critical infrastructure. The uncertainty (confidence) parameter is utilised, and it is subdivided into the following three basic categories: low uncertainty, medium uncertainty, and high uncertainty. The produced results demonstrate consistent applicability to empirical data analysis and real-world situations.

Key words: Disaster, geological hazards, geological risk mapping, landslide susceptibility

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1. Introduction

The high frequency of landslides, which can result in the destruction of infrastructure and structures, historical sites, disturbance of land use, risks to human health, etc., makes it necessary to evaluate the risk of landslides. Numerous landslide processes develop on the territory of Bulgarian according to its geological-tectonic parameters and relief. Extended investigations and practical endeavors concerning landslides have resulted in the identification of significant correlations regarding their distribution, activation and occurrence variables, processes, and dynamics.

The concept of risk is human-centered, and the process of assessing risk is a multifaceted endeavor that lacks a universally applicable model. The existing body of literature demonstrates that methods for assessing landslide risk are intricate and necessitate a substantial quantity of input data (Bonnard et al. 2005; Clague and Stead 2012; Asian Development Bank 2021; Lee and Jones 2023).

Three main landslide risk assessment approaches are widely used throughout the world. They are qualitative, semiquantitative and quantitative approaches (Regmi and Agrawal 2022). A relationship between significant factors affecting the landslide risk has also been studied by a number of authors (Rosser et al. 2021; Dhungana et al. 2023; Esposito et al. 2023; Kuhn et al. 2023). At the time, research done in Bulgaria is based on the United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR) and Inter-American Development Bank (IADB) methodology (Lakov et al. 2002; Dobrev et al. 2014; Frantsova 2021; Ivanov et al. 2022).

The paper presents the landslide risk assessment and scientific research carried out within the project „Landslides Risk in Bulgaria. Technical Annex 4“ under the World Bank project Reimbursable Advisory Services on Accelerating Resilience to Disaster Risks (P170629); Component 3: National Disaster Risk Profile (The World Bank in Bulgaria 2020).

The main methodology is based on International Standards IEC 31010:2019 Risk management—Risk assessment techniques and JRC-EC recommendation (Poljanšek et al. 2019).

The long-term research and applied activities on landslides by a number of Bulgarian authors, such as Berov et al. (2002), Bruchev et al. (2007), Ivanov et al. (2017b, 2022), Bruchev (2018), have led to the establishment of important dependencies for their distribution, factors for occurrence and activation, mechanism and dynamics, etc. Also, through remote sensing, from aerial and satellite instruments, an assessment of the danger of landslide processes along the northern Black Sea coast in Bulgaria was made by Atanasova and Nikolov (2021), Yamaguchi et al. (2021), Nikolov and Atanasova (2023).

Based on the available and accessible information on registered landslides in Bulgaria, some characteristic sections of the widespread landslide phenomena in certain landslide areas were selected.

The article examines one of three possible examples or case studies, conditionally divided into high, medium and low according to the degree of complexity and landslide activity carrying the corresponding risk. The present work aims to present the case study for a selected region in which to assess the landslide hazard and risk, under relatively favorable conditions for the slope stability and the engineering geological conditions of the geomorphological and geological forms of the considered terrain.

In order to fulfil the risk assessment criteria, set by the World Bank (WB), three hypothetical scenarios are selected for three distinct locations. These scenarios vary in terms of the likelihood of occurrence: low probability scenario, medium probability scenario and high probability.

The article specifically focuses on landslides in an urbanized area of Kavarna town. The main objective of the study is to carry out a risk assessment that estimates the potential damages and losses prior to a predefined likelihood of occurrence—low probability (unlikely) scenario.

The main tasks performed in the sequence of the research are: the determination of vulnerability and exposure data, the classification of landslides by groups—based on their activity and the risk they pose.

The determination of the risk elements based on economic and social significance and determined by degree of activity, types of landslides by area, urbanization of the territory and types of endangered sites.

Next is the determination of the main tasks such as the selection of landslide hazard data, hazard levels according to slope inclination, according to geological structure and scenario for seismically induced landslide.

All these steps are followed and strictly described in the methodological part of the study and the expected results of the relevant assumptions for determining the scenario.

2. Data and methods

To achieve the aim of the study, we chose to apply a methodology for building an integrated risk assessment based on scenario development in accordance with the IEC 31010:2019 recommendation.

There are some required steps that have to be followed in order to appropriately evaluate the landslide impact that are described in JRC-EC recommendation (Poljanšek et al. 2019).

National Disaster Risk Profile of Bulgaria (Ministry of Interior 2020) is the original document on which the present research is based.

The data and methods used for risk assessment are presented below as well as in a previous publication (Dobrev et al. 2023a) by the same team.

2.1. Methodology

According to globally accepted terminology, landslides are defined as the movement of a significant amount of earth mass down a slope, which occurs mainly due to the force of gravity (USGS 2021). The Program for the Prevention and Mitigation of Landslides on the Territory of the Republic of Bulgaria (Dobrev et al. 2023b) and in the Geological Risk Mapping (Ivanov et al. 2017a) consider certain types of slope movements from the Varnes classification (Varnes 1978), namely “rotational landslides”, “translational landslides”, “lateral spreads”, “earthflows” and “complex landslides”. In the article below, we refer only to these phenomena and as “landslides”. This is also the approach regarding the assessment of the risk of landslides, adopted by the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (MRDPW).

In the present study, the experience of some European countries (European Soil Data Centre 2023) in the assessment of landslide susceptibility and landslide risk was very useful, such as the landslide risk assessment procedures in Austria (Schweigl and Hervás 2009), Greece (ThinkHazard 2020) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (EU Floods recovery Programme 2015), the risk assessment guidelines of the Joint Research Center of the European Union, the guidelines for disaster risk management of the Australian Society of Geomechanics (Walker et al. 2007), and the approach to risk assessment of natural phenomena used in the National Risk Profile of the Netherlands (National Risk Profile 2016).

The preparation of various maps, such as distribution maps, susceptibility maps, hazard maps, and risk maps, is a key component of landslide risk assessment (Fell et al. 2008; Ivanov et al. 2017b, 2022). The following function is used for risk calculation:

$$R = f(V,H,E) \tag{1}$$

where risk (R) depends on vulnerability (V), hazard (H) and exposure (E) (Poljanšek et al. 2019).

Methods for hazard, vulnerability and exposure assessment are described in detail in Frantsova (2021). This methodology was used to assess a complex level of risk from geological processes on the example of the northern Bulgarian Black Sea coast region (Frantsova 2023).

Landslide susceptibility for Bulgaria is presented in Fig.1 as well as the location of the study area (Kavarna town). The map was helpful in selecting an area suitable for the scenario described in the present study. Namely, a low probability scenario—activation of a landslide in the town of Kavarna.

Figure 1. Landslide susceptibility map of Bulgaria (after Ivanov et al. 2017b) with the location of the study area (red rectangle).

2.2. Vulnerability and exposure data

The landslide risk assessment (risk scenario) is directly related to analysis of exposure and hazard (Dobrev et al. 2014). The assessment encompasses many attributes (point-scored indicators) associated with the condition of landslides and the components of risk expressed by:

$$P_i = S * E \tag{2}$$

Where: P_i —indicator, S —characteristic of the state of landslides, E —elements of risk.

Formula 2 can be represented as a sum and multiplication of elements concerning the features (characteristics) of the landslide process and risk elements. This is presented by formula 3:

$$P_i = (S_1 + S_2) * (E_1 + E_2) \tag{3}$$

The current situation regarding landslides (S) is determined by:

- degree of activity S1 (Table 1);
- size/volume S2 (Table 2).

The elements at risk are based on economic and social significance (E) and are determined by:

- urbanization of the territory E1 (Table 3);
- category of endangered sites E2 (Table 4).

Table 1. Landslides by level of activity (modified after UNESCO/WPWL 1993).

Determination by degree of activity, S1	Points
Active, with periodic activity	4
Potentially hazardous landslide-prone areas (dormant landslides)	3
Stabilized incl. ancient landslides and reinforced landslides	1

Table 2. Scale of landslide processes (Dobrev et al. 2014, 2023b).

Types of landslides by area, S2	Points
Area over 20 000 m ² (class I)	4
Area from 10 000 to 20 000 m ² (class II)	3
Area from 1 000 to 10 000 m ² (class III)	2
Area less than 1 000 m ² (class IV)	1

Table 3. Urbanization of the territory and endangered sites.

Urbanization of the territory and types of endangered sites, E1	Points *
Residential buildings, schools, hospitals, public buildings	5
Motorways and/or national roads class I, railways, dam facilities of national importance	5
Endangered cultural and historical monuments, sites of national and international importance	5
Republican roads class II, III and IV, dam facilities of regional importance	4
Municipal roads, streets, alleys, beaches, industrial buildings, massive buildings in villa areas, landfills, electricity distribution and transmission grid facilities, communication facilities	3
Temporary buildings, lighthouses	2
Arable lands	2
Agricultural lands - uncultivated (meadows), forest fund and areas specified in the registration table as "land" or "property"	1

* Maximum total number of points is 21 according to the Methodology for assessment of geological risk (Dobrev et al. 2014) and Program for the prevention and mitigation of landslides on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria, erosion and abrasion along the Danube and Black Sea coasts for the period 2022–2027 (Dobrev et al. 2023b).

Table 4. Category of endangered sites (Dobrev et al. 2014).

Category of endangered sites, E2	Points
Residential and public buildings over 15 m high, highways and roads class I, main railway lines, facilities of national and regional importance	4
Residential and public buildings 10 to 15 m high, roads class II and III, railway lines not specified in category A, facilities of regional importance	3
Residential and public buildings up to 10 m high, roads and facilities of local importance	2
Light structure buildings, temporary buildings, local roads allowing for by-passing, forest and agricultural roads	1

Landslides are categorized into three groups based on these priority criteria (according to the points obtained), depending on the level of activity and risk they pose (Dobrev et al. 2014, 2023b):

- Group I—for priority implementation of countermeasures and activities;
- Group II—for carrying out preventive measures and/or geo-protective measures and activities;
- Group III—for monitoring.

2.3 Landslide hazard data

The approach utilised for assessing the hazard and risk associated with landslides is described in Methodology for geological risk assessment (Dobrev et al. 2014). This methodology is subsequently applied in the development of geological risk mapping. The primary component of the input data (Ivanov et al. 2017c) can be seen in Tables 5–8. The landslide susceptibility map of the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, used the Mora & Vahrson method (Mora and Vahrson 1994), complemented and modified by Berov et al. (2016, 2020), Ivanov et al. (2020).

Table 5. Landslide occurrence probability classification (P). Source: Fell (1994), Dobrev et al. (2014).

P	Description	Annually
12	Extremely high	1
8	Very high	0.2
5	High	0.05
3	Medium	0.01
2	Low	0.001

Table 6. Classification by landslide hazard ($H = M * P$). Source: Fell (1994), Dobrev et al. (2014). The levels are derived from statistical data considering research and monitoring of about 900 landslides in Bulgaria.

H	Category
≥ 30	Extremely high
$\geq 20 - < 30$	Very high
$\geq 10 - < 20$	High
$\geq 7 - < 10$	Medium
$\geq 3 - < 7$	Low
≥ 2	Very low

Table 7. Hazard levels according to slope inclination (α).

α	Inclination range, degrees
0	>45
2	30–45
3	24–30
5	18–24
8	15–18
9	12–15
10	9–12
5	5–9
0	< 5

Table 8. Hazard levels according to geological structure (G).

G	Geological description
7	Quaternary (clay, sandy clay)
10	Neogene (clay, sandy clay)
6	Paleogene (stiff clays)
5	Quaternary and Cenozoic coarse-grained sediments, slightly lithified
4	Mesozoic (rocks and weak rocks)
2	Paleozoic and Precambrian (rocks)

The landslide magnitude (M) shall be approximated utilising the formula:

$$M = \alpha * G * k \tag{4}$$

where, α is the threat level according to slope inclination and G is the threat level according to geological structure (Ivanov et al. 2017b). The purpose of the coefficient k that is used in the formula is to make the result that is obtained equal to the magnitude of the final values (Dobrev et al. 2023a, 2023b; Frantzo-va 2023). Through the use of this coefficient k, Fell’s seven magnitude classes (Fell 1994) can be related to this methodology, i.e. the highest magnitude value cannot exceed 7 (Dobrev et al. 2014).

The assessment of the landslide hazard is determined through statistical analysis of data obtained from information maps sourced from the National landslide registry of Bulgaria. Two primary factors considered are the geological composition of the formations where landslides occur and the steepness of the slopes.

Information from a total of 916 registered landslides is utilised. Each indication has a maximum score of 10 points. The Neogene formations, which are more prone to landslide occurrences, receive the highest score in indication G, which assesses the geological structure. Regarding the second indication, statistical data reveals that the highest frequency of landslides occurs within the range of 12–15° slope inclination, with a total of 10 point.

3. Risk assessment via impact and low probability scenario for seismically induced landslide

The presented scenario provides a comprehensive description of the circumstances, triggers and potential outcomes associated with the risk events. On the other hand, each complex scenario is based on an expert theoretical proposition derived from available data and knowledge. The probability (or likelihood) of the selected scenario occurring in the next five years has a 119-year return period (low probability scenario).

3.1 Low probability scenario—seismically induced landslide (Kavarna region)

The scenario is set in an urban town (Kavarna) on the northern Black Sea coast of Bulgaria. This area (between Varna and Kavarna) is known for its large landslides (Berov et al. 2013; Evlogiev and Evstatiev 2013; Nankin and Ivanov 2019; Atanasova and Nikolov 2021). The main part of the town is located on a plateau and its foothills reach above the sea. The rest of the town is situated on the slope of a large erosional valley that descends to the sea.

The town is moderately economically developed: About 60% of the population is of working age, while the unemployment rate for 2020 is 6.2%. The town has about 10000 inhabitants, with about 2500 residential buildings and almost 4000 apartments. There are three schools, three kindergartens, a large municipal hospital, and twenty hotels, villas, and guesthouses of varying capacity. The largest hotel can accommodate 400 people. The total capacity of the hotels in the valley is about 2000 people. Most of the town is located on the plateau, but 17 houses are built on the slope and on the edge of the plateau. On the slopes of the valley there are the history museum, the cultural monument “Hamama”, a pumping station, hotels and cottages. A power line runs across the slope.

Part of the town—from the plateau on the slopes to the sea—consists of a deluvial cover several meters thick (Cheshitev et al. 1991). The aragonite sediments (Koleva-Rekalova 1994; Nankin et al. 2022; Yaneva et al. 2019) of the Topola Formation (N_1^s), which are characterized by special physical and mechanical indicators, are of great importance for the landslide processes. They are unstable to dynamic impacts. Landslides often occur on the sediments of the Euxinograd Formation (N_1^s) (Fig. 2).

The scenario develops in daytime, at the beginning of the tourist season.

Initial conditions: A long period with light and continuous rainfall is a prerequisite for slow runoff and water saturation of deluvial deposits on the slope. An earthquake from the Shabla-Kaliakra zone is a triggering and destabilizing factor with a magnitude over five and intensity $I \geq VII$ degree (MSK scale). Landslides (Fig. 3, 4) are activated quickly and without warning. In the uppermost area of the valley, part of the slope between the church and the Dobrotitsa Hotel (central part of the town of Kavarna) slides down. Shallow landslides affect different parts of the valley slopes.

The landslide in the resort part of the port is activated. Seventeen houses are deformed and destroyed; hotels in the landslide area are cracked and are deformed. Thirty people are left without shelter; about four hundred tourists are evacuated from the hotels. The church is damaged. A power line is cut and a

Figure 2. Geological map of the area (after Cheshitev et al. (1991)).

Figure 3. Location of the landslides (Kavarna Region). Indicative level of hazard according to equation (2) ranging from 0 to 1. Legend: 0.1—very low; 0.4—low; 0.6—medium; 1—very high. With a red triangle—the location of Cape Chirakman (ancient city of Bizone).

Figure 4. View of the considered area. **A** the valley descending to the sea, built up in the lower part **B** the left valley slope **C** the left valley slope by the sea **D** Cape Chirakman (near the Kavarna port)—the site of the ancient town of Bizone, which sank into the sea in the first century B.C. after a strong earthquake and a resulting landslide.

pumping station is damaged. The road to the port is interrupted in a few places. A local road, passing through the resort, is severely distorted. Access to the history museum has also been cut off.

Commercial fishing, canned seafood manufacturing, and museum operations are anticipated to be suspended. The tourist industry is to be hampered for a long period. Nearly 530 people will lose their jobs. Of these, 320 are temporarily and 210 for a longer period. Unemployment will rise temporarily to 12.6%, but for a longer period, to 8.7%. There are no casualties among the tourists. 1–2 people with limited mobility were injured during the evacuation.

Access to the resort area is difficult. The main road is interrupted, and it will take about a week to clear it. The short road from the resort area to the plateau is distorted, and deformations will continue for several months until movements subside. For this reason, it is urgent to build a new road of about 400 m from the plateau to the hotels in order to carry out restoration work. It is possible to use the port for evacuation as well as helicopters. There are difficulties in medical care, as three out of the 30 medics in town live in the affected houses in the area.

The area has high seismicity (Table 9) (Solakov et al. 2022). The consequences in the Republic of Bulgaria of the Vrancea earthquake in 1977 (including slope deformations) are described by Brankov (1983). Publications discussing the occurrence of landslides caused by seismic activity and the assessment of geodynamic hazards and risks along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast are presented in the works of Iliev (1973), Konstantinov et al. (1992), Lakov et al. (2002). Near the port of Kavarna is Cape Chirakman—the site of the ancient town of Bizone, which sank into the sea in the first century B.C. after a strong

Table 9. Seismic data of the study area.

Date	Coordinates	Magnitude	Depth, km	Intensity *	Source
15.07.2015	N43.29/E28.41	4.3	15	IV	EMSC
03.12.2012	N43.41/E28.65	4.9	10	V	EMSC
11.10.2011	N43.60/E28.53	4.1	15	IV–V	EMSC
05.08.2009	N43.45/E28.69	5.0	10	VI	USGS
30.06.1956	N43.6/E28.5	5.4	60	VI–VII	BCEQ
08.09.1911	N43.4/E28.1	4.8	10	VI	BCEQ
08.02.1904	N43.5/2E8.5	4.5	15	V–VI	BCEQ
25.05.1902	N43.5/E28.5	4,5	10	VI	BCEQ
30.06.1901	N43.4/E28.5	6.0	10	VII–VIII	BCEQ
06.06.1901	N43.4/E28.3	5.2	10	VII	BCEQ
26.04.1901	N43.4/E28.5	4.5	10	VI	BCEQ
25.04.1901	N43.4/E28.5	5.0	10	VI–VII	BCEQ
31.03.1901	N43.4/E28.7	7.2	14	IX	BCEQ
1832	N43.3/E28.4	-	-	VIII	BCEQ

Note: *—Intensity in the area of the considered scenario, EMSC—Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre (EMSC 2023), USGS—U.S. Geological Survey (USGS 2023), BCEQ—Balkan catalogue of earthquakes (Shebalin et al. 1974; AHEAD 2023).

Table 10. Input data used to calculate the probability of an earthquake with intensity above V in the study area.

Period	No. of years	Cases	Return interval, RI (years)	Probability of occurrence in 5 years, P
1901–2012	112	6	18.67	23%
1902–2020	119	1	119	4%

Note: 6 aftershocks for the period 1901–1904 are not included.

earthquake and a resulting landslide (Evstatiev et al. 2021). In 1901, the region was shaken by a strong earthquake of magnitude $M=7.2$ (Watzof 1903). Seismogenic faults in the area and their role in shallow methane seeps southeast of Kavarna as possible precursors of sea earthquakes is reviewed by Parlichev and Vasilev (2021).

Traces of shallow landslides (Fig. 3) can still be observed along both banks of the valley. A landslide has occurred in the area near the port, where most of the hotels are built. Activation after rains in 2004 is known, because of which two villas were destroyed. Retention walls have been built.

A 4% probability of landslide activation within 5 years has been calculated.

Other main characteristics related to the hazard and susceptibility to landslide processes, such as lithology, soil humidity, seismicity-triggering hazards, and precipitation-triggering hazards, are presented in Ivanov et al. (2020), and Berov et al. (2020).

3.2. Results

The acquired results demonstrate a comprehensive landslides risk assessment by applying the scenario-development approach.

The results are presented in a tabular format (Table 11), focusing five national interests: physical safety, security of physical assets and critical infrastructure, economic security, social well-being, and natural environment security specific to Bulgaria.

Table 11. Landslides scenario impact summary (town of Kavarna)—population and infrastructure impacts.

Scenario likelihood							
	Almost certain	Very likely	Likely	Unlikely	Very rare	Extremely rare	Explanation
Likelihood of scenario occurring in the next 5 years				X			119-year return period
Scenario impact							
National interest	Impact criterion	Impact severity					Explanation of the impact
		Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Catastrophic	
Physical safety	Fatalities		X				1–2 fatalities in houses located on the slope
	Injured and chronically ill	X					2–3 cases of injuries due to difficult evacuation
	People requiring temporary accommodations or permanently displaced			X			About 500 people will be evacuated, most of them tourists; about 30 locals will need to be permanently moved to stable terrain
Security of physical assets and critical infrastructure	Damage to buildings		X				Damage and destruction of houses located on the slope and of resort hotels
	Damage to cultural heritage			X			Serious damage to church; interrupted/difficult access to the museum
	Damage to CI and disruption to operation of CI			X			Shaft wells (for water supply), pump station, water supply system, and sewerage system are affected; parts of the electricity transmission network are affected
Economic security	Impact on the economy		X				Tourism and commercial fishing are affected
	Impact on key economic sectors				X		Hotels could be affected during the tourist season
Social well-being	Disruption of everyday life			X			Lack of electricity and water for a short period
	Income loss and unemployment		X				Local economy will not stop working, but jobs will be affected by decrease in tourism
	Disruption to key societal functions	X					No disruption
Natural environment security	Destruction of natural assets		X				Impact on the habitat of some rare birds
	Long-term disruptions to the environment	X					No impact

Note: grey = low uncertainty; yellow = medium uncertainty; red = high uncertainty. The levels are described in details in Dobrev et al. (2023a).

The table presents a defined set of impact criteria for each national interest. The significance scale utilized for rating each impact criterion encompasses a range of categories, namely insignificant, minor, moderate, major, and catastrophic impacts.

The Uncertainty (confidence) parameter is applied to reflect the reliability of the data used. It is expressed qualitatively and ranges from low confidence (inconclusive evidence or disagreement among experts) to very high confidence (strong evidence and high consensus).

Severity impact essentially refers to the quantitative level of the risk, respectively vulnerability and exposure.

The outcomes of the given scenario acknowledge the primary risks linked to: impact on key economic sectors, people requiring temporary accommodations or permanently displaced, disruption of everyday life and damage to critical infrastructure.

The high levels of exposure of structures in the area of interest can be seen as having a significant impact on important economic sectors. The primary consequences that need to be addressed are related to social systems and infrastructure—people requiring temporary accommodations or permanently displaced, damage to critical infrastructure and disruption to everyday life. Since the impact severity is only expected to be moderate, no fatalities or significant injuries will be expected.

On the other hand, more investigation is required for the most severe situations with the lowest probability to allow for an in-depth analysis and risk assessment for the area in question.

4. Discussion and perspectives

By considering these perspectives and integrating their findings, risk assessment experts can develop comprehensive strategies for landslide risk management, including early warning systems, land-use planning, and mitigation measures.

Risk assessment for landslides involves considering various perspectives to ensure a comprehensive evaluation. Here are some key perspectives to consider:

1. Geological and engineering geological perspective: Engineer geologists play a crucial role in assessing landslide risks. They study the geological conditions, such as slope stability, rock types, soil composition, and past landslide occurrences, to identify areas prone to landslides.
2. Topographical perspective: Topographic data, including elevation, slope steepness, and drainage patterns, are essential for evaluating landslide risks. Steep slopes, concave terrain, and areas with poor drainage are more susceptible to landslides.
3. Hydrological and hydrogeological perspective: Understanding the hydrological and hydrogeological conditions is vital as water plays a significant role in triggering landslides. Factors such as rainfall patterns, groundwater levels, and the presence of water bodies near slopes contribute to landslide susceptibility.
4. Climate perspective: Climate change can influence landslide risks. Assessing long-term climate patterns, including changes in precipitation,

temperature, and extreme weather events, helps determine if landslides are likely to increase or decrease in the future.

5. Human activities perspective: Human activities, such as deforestation, urbanization, mining, and construction, can significantly impact landslide risks. Assessing land-use changes and their effects on slope stability is essential to understand the human-induced factors contributing to landslides.
6. Historical perspective: Examining historical landslide events in the area provides valuable insights into recurring patterns, identifying high-risk zones, and understanding the factors that triggered past landslides.
7. Technological perspective: Advances in technology, such as remote sensing, LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging), and satellite imagery, can aid in landslide risk assessment. These tools help in mapping and monitoring terrain changes, detecting ground movement, and identifying potential landslide-prone areas.
8. Socio-economic perspective: Assessing the vulnerability of communities living in landslide-prone areas is crucial. Factors such as population density, infrastructure vulnerability, and socioeconomic conditions help determine the potential impact and consequences of landslides on human lives and property.

The current assessment is being done for the first time and its main purpose is to serve as a model for subsequent assessments for other regions, in Bulgaria or abroad, where similar geological and infrastructural conditions exist.

5. Conclusion

The study provides a methodology for building an integrated risk assessment based on scenario development as recommended by IEC 31010:2019. The methodology was created and implemented for the initial evaluation of landslide hazards and risk in Bulgaria. The impact of landslides on the elements at risk is assessed by following mandatory procedures.

Scenarios are categorised into three primary types: high probability scenarios, medium probability scenarios, and low probability scenarios. The previous study conducted by Dobrev et al. (2023a) provides the data and methodologies utilised for risk assessment. It also presents a probable (likely) scenario, namely the possibility of a landslide occurring within the next five years, along a mountain road.

The present article presents a rare situation (unlikely scenario) that describes the possibility of landslide activation in the vicinity of the town of Kavarna, located on the northern shore of the Black Sea in Bulgaria under certain impacts.

In order to attain outcomes that are highly credible, the uncertainty (confidence) parameter is employed, and it is categorised into three primary levels: low, medium, and high uncertainty. The data collected for the current scenario exhibit a strong correlation with actual events, the examination of empirical data, and the authors' personal investigations. The collaborative efforts of the authors, who conducted field research and individually evaluated specific hypotheses, enhanced the trustworthiness of the findings. Through the engineering-geological research of the area in question, the different assumptions regarding the level of overall risk were confirmed. Prior to this, surveys were

carried out among the municipal personnel who are accountable for the planning and implementation of civil infrastructure projects. The authors ensure the veracity of all the data they used.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.